

Reaction (a) involves the ionisation of the organic reducer in presence of a suitable medium giving rise to reactive hydrogen ions which are extremely powerful reducers. This reaction is also brought about by the well known oxidising action of silver halides on the organic developers. In reaction (b) part of development occurs, when the silver ions attain electroneutrality. Reactions (c) and (e) are typical hydrolytic oxidation-reduction reactions where sodium sulphite plays the most important part. It acts as a stain preventive preservative, and more important of both as hydrogen acceptor with a dual rôle, since in two hydrolytic oxidation-reduction reactions it regenerates the original developer (*vide e*) and reduces an amount of the silver ions (*vide e*) by abstracting away their positive charges. The silver formed in (b) and in (e) in solution, soon becomes saturated and equilibrium is attained. The organic developers function as hydrogen donators (*vide a*) and inductors (*vide e*) which is the secondary reaction and which is induced by the primary reaction namely the oxidation of the easily oxidisable substances such as hydroquinone, pyrogallol, metol, etc.

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Studies On Optical Activity and Chemical Constitution. Part I. Optically Active Bases and Acids.

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Phenylenebisiminocamphor (I) (Forster and Thornley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 942), 1:4 naphthylenebisiminocamphor (II) (Singh and Singh, *ibid.*, 1920, 117, 1599), camphorylamino phenyliminocamphor (III) (Forster and Saville, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 789) and *pp'*s diphenylaminobisiminocamphor (IV) (Singh, Singh and Lal, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 1971) are examples of substances possessing very high rotatory powers. All of them contain an optimum association of azethenoid groups, conjugated linkages and a benzene or a naphthalene ring within a narrow

molecular compass. Working on these lines, Patel and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 87) have prepared 1:4-naphthylenebisiminocamphor (V) which has a remarkably high rotatory power $[\alpha]_{3780}^{25} = 3340.9^\circ$ (pyridine).

This paper describes the condensation products of camphorquinone and *m*- and *p*-aminodimethylanilines. *p*-Dimethylaminophenyliminocamphor (VI) is endowed with very high specific rotatory powers even though it does not possess the essentials of the above-mentioned compounds. The following table records the rotatory powers of the above compounds together with the rotatory powers of *p*-dimethylaminophenyliminocamphor.

TABLE I.

I. 1:4-Phenylenebisiminocamphor

II. 1:4-Naphthylenebisiminocamphor

III. Camphorylaminoxyphenyliminocamphor

Rule and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 178; 1929, 2277) in the case of *p*-substituted octyl benzoates have also observed that the $N(\text{Me})_2$ and NH_2 groups give exaltation of rotation. In this case the increase in $[\text{M}]_{5461}$ is from -92° to -163° and -231° respectively.

It is commonly known that the rotations of acids and bases often diminish in magnitude or become reversed in sign when the compounds are ionised. This is very marked if the basic group is the only group of high polar character in the molecule.

Many cases of such a fall in the rotatory power are recorded in literature. Among these may be mentioned *d*-amylamine, *l*-nicotine, conine and 1:4'-amino-4-methyldiphenylsulphoxide, all of which undergo a reversal of sign of rotation in hydrochloric acid solution.

When a drop of methyl iodide was added to an alcoholic solution and kept overnight, the rotatory power fell from $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} = 2487^\circ$ to $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} = 1973^\circ$. This may be attributed to the ionisation of the methiodide compound formed.

p-Dimethylaminophenyliminocamphor was examined in benzaldehyde. It has $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} = 1924^\circ$, an exceptionally low figure when compared with the values obtained in other solvents. This value fell to $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} = 1471^\circ$, and the colour of the solution changed from deep yellow to light greenish yellow. A fresh solution in benzaldehyde was examined and gave $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} = 1429^\circ$, which after three days fell to $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} = 304^\circ$. The maximum rotation is obtained with benzaldehyde from freshly opened bottle. This value could not be repeated. The rapid fall of value in the first solution and the successive fresh solutions can be explained by the fact that benzaldehyde is partially oxidised to benzoic acid, which forms a salt with the basic substance.

The rotatory power of *m*-dimethylaminophenyliminocamphor is considerably lower than that of the *para* isomer. The rotatory powers of some *meta* derivatives of phenyliminocamphor are given below:

[α] _D (chloroform).					
-Br	-Cl	-COOH	-OH	-N(Me) ₂	-H
418°	499°	470°	630°	662°	726°

Although the value for the dimethylamino compound is lower than the unsubstituted compound, it is greater than that of any other compound.

Effect of Solvent.

The ideal conditions to study solvent influences are best observed with optically active compounds of simple molecular structure with a strongly polar group situated near the asymmetric carbon atom. The compound under observation certainly contains a strongly polar group $N(Me)_2$, but is not simple in structure.

The dimethylamino derivatives of phenyliminocamphor have been examined polarimetrically in twelve solvents and, in the case of the *m*-compound, and also in three wave-lengths. It is found that using solvents of the general formula C_6H_5X , the increase in the rotatory power due to the variation of 'X' in the solvent molecule is expressed by

With the exception of the nitro group, this series corresponds with the one that represents the effect of the substituents when introduced into the optically active molecule.

Solvent. C_6H_6 . PhMe. PhCl. PhBr. PhI. $PhNO_2$. $PhNH_2$.
p-Dimethyl 2461° 2396° 2551° 2786° 2851° 2986° 3000°

It has been observed that the dimethylamino group increases the rotation of phenyliminocamphor to a remarkable extent and it is significant that this effect is maximum in the case of aniline, a solvent which contains a strongly polar NH_2 group. In the case of non-benzenoid solvents the order is $C_5H_5N > CS_2 > C_2H_5OH > CHCl_3 > MeOH$

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Dimethylaminophenyliminocamphor.—Equimolecular quantities of camphorquinone and *p*-aminodimethylaniline were dissolved in absolute alcohol, a little anhydrous sodium sulphate added, and the solution heated on a water-bath under reflux for 3 hours. After evaporating off the excess of alcohol, the solution was cooled and poured into water. The condensation product settled together with a considerable amount of tarry matter. It was extracted with 50-60% alcohol and recrystallised as a light brown fluffy crystalline mass, m. p. 135.5° after deepening in colour.

The yield did not improve even when the reactant substances were heated dry with a little anhydrous sodium sulphate without alcohol. It was readily soluble in methyl or ethyl alcohol, benzene,

carbon disulphide, chloroform and other organic solvents, but insoluble in water.

The substance in alcoholic solution behaves as an indicator similar to methyl orange. It dyes wool yellow. (Found: N, 10.02. $C_{18}H_{24}ON_2$ requires N, 9.86 per cent).

m-Dimethylaminophenyliminocamphor.—Molecular proportions of camphorquinone and *m*-aminodimethylaniline in absolute alcoholic solution with a little or no anhydrous sodium sulphate, were refluxed on a water-bath for 3-4 hours. After evaporating off the excess of alcohol, the product was cooled, water added and the whole solution left overnight. The impure product was further twice crystallised from 50% alcohol in beautiful yellow needle-like crystals, melting at 125-26° after changing to a red colour. It is very readily soluble in methyl or ethyl alcohol, benzene, carbon disulphide, etc and soluble in water. (Found: N, 10.1. $C_{18}H_{24}ON_2$ requires N, 9.86 per cent).

Condensation between camphorquinone and *o*-aminodimethylaniline under similar conditions gave a viscous mass which could not be crystallised.

TABLE II.

Specific rotations of p-dimethylaminophenyliminocamphor.

Solvent.	Conc.	Temp.	$[\alpha]_D$.
C_6H_6	0.0197 g./25 c.c.	18°	2462
C_6H_5Me	0.0240	18	2396
$C_6H_5NO_2$	0.0252	18	2986
C_6H_5Cl	0.0246	18	2551
C_6H_5Br	0.0245	18	2786
C_6H_5I	0.0253	18	2851
$C_6H_5NH_2$	0.0320	34	3000
C_6H_5CHO	0.0204	19	1924
C_5H_5N	0.0258	19	2791
MeOH	0.0421	20	2352
EtOH	0.0560	22	2487
$CHCl_3$	0.0123	32	2358
CS_2	0.0265	19	2726

The readings for other wave-lengths could not be taken as the solution was too dark.

TABLE III.

Specific rotations of m-dimethylaminophenyliminocamphor.

Solvent.	Conc.	Temp.	$[\alpha]_D$.	$[\alpha]_{3700}$.	$[\alpha]_{6461}$.
C_6H_6	0.0417g/25 c.c.	27°	710°	782°	956°
C_6H_5Me	0.0490	27	653	755	944
$C_6H_5NO_2$	0.0488	27	697	790	980
C_6H_5Cl	0.0398	34	647	773	1005
C_6H_5Br	0.0482	27	918	1005	1306
C_6H_5CHO	0.0396	34	568	—	—
C_6H_5CHO	After 27 hours		436	—	—
C_5H_5N	0.0391	27°	723	774	910
MeOH	0.0466	29	628	655	767
$(Me)_2CO$	0.0394	34	584	628	812
CS_2	0.0324	27	756	787	1080
$CHCl_3$	0.0400	32	663	738	963
$C_6H_5NH_2$	0.0488	27	711	793	1009

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